

The nervous system explanation of meridian Science

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Abstract

Meridian science has definite therapeutic effect, but it lacks the corresponding anatomical structure, that is, it cannot be strictly matched with the nervous system. This problem has existed for a long time. Now, I have found the answer: the circuit provided by meridian science is a "functional connection", not an actual circuit.

Text

The lines described by meridian science are called "meridians", and the functional points are called "acupoints". The "meridians" are expressed by lines connecting the "acupoints". This explains why the route of "meridians" does not strictly match the nervous system, because it is the result of functional connection. If we use the highway system to compare, the principle is very intuitive.

Figure 1

"Acupoints" are essentially some functional points of the nervous system, and "meridians" are the connecting lines of these functional points. There are two strong reasons to support this judgment:

1. The nervous system is the fastest signal transmission system in the human body, and the "meridians" have a similar transmission speed.
2. The human body has no second nervous system, which violates the principle of biological evolution efficiency.

Discuss

"Meridian science" is essentially a collection and collation of the specific applications of the nervous system by the ancients. It is a database of the application cases of the nervous system. It is of great value to the study of the nervous system today. For example, it provides the possibility of brain computer interface beyond the head. It is a common situation that the application is ahead of the theoretical explanation, which leads to the fog of "meridian science" for a long time. Now, the fog has been dispelled.